

**12th International Conference on
Predictive Modelling in Food
ICPMF12**

**13 – 16 June 2023
Sapporo, Japan
Hokkaido University Conference Hall**

Preface

Dear Colleagues and friends,

On behalf of organizing committee of the 12th International Conference on Predictive Modelling in Foods (ICPMF12), we would like to welcome you to Hokkaido University, Sapporo, Japan. It is our great honor and pleasure to host the first ICPMF in Japan and Asia since 1992. In addition, we are very pleased and excited to meet all of you in person overcoming Covid-19 pandemic last couple of years. While we have been able to communicate with colleagues and friends virtually, we recognize that face-to-face interactions are invaluable. The ICPMF12 was originally scheduled in 2021 after successful ICPMF11 in Bragança, but we have to postpone to 2023. Therefore, we have insisted on holding the conference in person to become the opportunity to meet again colleagues and re-boot research activity on predictive microbiology. We hope that the ICPMF12 will revitalize our research community and inspire new collaborations.

Unexpectedly, this year 2023 is 30th memorial year of predictive microbiology. The first monograph of predictive microbiology, which is well-known as "RED BOOK" was published in 1993. We believe that it is a great opportunity to review the progress of the research field so far, and prospect the future development of predictive modeling studies. Unfortunately, Professor Thomas A. McMeekin, who is one of the authors of the "RED Book" and did all the hard work internationally, passed away in 2021. We would like to take this opportunity to acknowledge Tom's huge contribution to predictive microbiology research field.

Software development has been playing an important role in progress of predictive microbiology. We are very pleased to hold the software fair in this conference since ICPMF9 in 2015 in Rio de Janeiro. Direct communication with software developers in person will offer new insights into the potential of predictive microbiology.

We are currently experiencing a significant shift in computational technologies, particularly with the rapid development of generative artificial intelligence (AI). We anticipate that the ways in which we approach predictive microbiology may soon evolve. To catch up with the changes of the time, we need to keep a sharp eye on technological advances and respond to them appropriately. In this sense, we believe that the symposium on machine learning at this conference will play an extremely important role.

Finally, We hope that you will have the opportunity to experience Japan's unique culture and cuisine, which is unlike any other in the world. We strongly believe that direct contact with different cultures and sharing time together with colleagues and friends is the real pleasure of an international conference and will lead to the future development of the research field. The organizing committee hopes that this conference will be a meaningful one for all of you.

with warmest regards,

Shige Koseki

Kento Koyama

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12th International Conference on Predictive Modelling in Food

June 13-16, 2023 Sapporo, Japan

Conference Program

Hokkaido University Conference Hall

Day 1:
Tuesday, June 13, 2023

Registration

Open from 13:00 -

Pre-conference Workshops 14:00-17:00

Workshop 1 <u>Exploiting the power of the harmonized knowledge exchange format FSKX</u>	Workshop 2 <u>Bayesian methods for microbiological data and risk assessment</u>	Workshop 3 <u>Introduction to Predictive Microbiology</u>	Workshop 4 <u>Meta-Regression in Food Microbiological Safety</u>
Matthias Filter German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR)	Dr. Jukka Ranta Finnish Food Authority	Dr. Lihan Huang Eastern Regional Research Center, Agricultural Research Service, U.S. Department of Agriculture Research Service	Dr. Ursula Gonzales-Barron Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Portugal Vasco Cadavez, Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Portugal
Meeting room #3	Meeting room #4	Meeting room #5	Meeting room #6

ICPMF Board Members Meeting

17:30 – 18:30 @Meeting room #2

Welcome Reception

18:00 – 20:00 @Information center (next to the conference venue)

Day 2: Wednesday, June 14, 2023

at 2F Auditorium

8:00-	Registration
9:00 -9:10	Welcome from the chair Shige Koseki and Kento Koyama (Hokkaido University) 🇯🇵
9:10 – 9:30	Predictive Microbiology: so far and the future 30th anniversary of the RED book Prof. Tom Ross (University of Tasmania) 🇦🇺
9:30 - 10:00	Keynote lecture 1 Variability and uncertainty in predictive microbiology and QMRA – the what, the why and the how Dr. Albert Garre (Technical University of Cartagena, Spain) 🇪🇸
10:00 - 10:30	Coffee break Poster session The presenters with “ odd number ” should stand by the poster (1F Hall)
10:30-12:00	Oral session 1: Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment Chairs: Marcel Zwietering & Hiroki Abe
10:30	O1-1 Characterization of uncertainty in microbiological risk assessment: is it possible? Maarten Nauta 🇩🇪
10:45	O1-2 Minimizing the risk of foodborne illness and analytical costs using a QMRA model for raw milk cheeses Subhasish Basak, Janushan Christy, Laurent Guillier, Frédérique Audiat-Perrin, Moez Sanaa, Fanny Tenenhaus-Aziza, Julien Bect, Emmanuel Vazquez 🇫🇷 🇨🇦
11:00	O1-3 Farm to fork quantitative risk assessment of <i>Escherichia coli</i> O157:H7 illness from the consumption of fresh Australian apples <u>Elizabeth Frankish</u> , Hayriye Bozkurt, Tom Ross 🇦🇺

11:15	<p>O1-4 Using the biorisk package for R to evaluate the risk of salmonellosis associated with fresh-cut lettuce production and distribution chains</p> <p><u>Arícia Possas</u>, Silvia Guillén, Pablo S. Fernandez, Fernando Pérez-Rodríguez, Alberto Garre 🇪🇸</p>
11:30	<p>O1-5 Joint FAO/WHO Expert meetings on microbiological risk assessment (JEMRA)</p> <p>Kang Zhou 🇮🇹</p>
11:45	<p>O1-6 Development of a Quantitative Microbiological Spoilage Risk Assessment (QMSRA) Model for fresh poultry fillets</p> <p><u>Sofia Tsaloumi</u>, Leonardos Stathas, Konstantinos Koutsoumanis 🇺🇸</p>
12:00-13:30	Lunch (HOTEL MYSTAYS Sapporo Aspen)
13:30-15:00	<p>Oral session 2: Predictive microbiology software development Chairs: Lihan Huang & Ursula Gonzales-Barron</p>
13:30	<p>O2-1 Sym'Previus MAP- A web application for the design of food packaging to improve the preservation of food products</p> <p>Jonathan Thévenot, <u>Yvan Le Marc</u>, Catherine Denis, Janushan Christy, Valérie Michel, Valérie Stahl, Didier Majou, Emilie Gauvry, Emmanuel Jamet, Fanny Tenenhaus-Aziza, Jean-Christophe Augustin, Narjes Mtimet, Guillier Laurent, Sabine Jeuge, Jeanne-Marie Membré, Anna Jofré, Alizée Guérin, Aline Rault, Stella Planchon, Olivier Couvert, Louis Coroller 🇫🇷 🇪🇸</p>
13:45	<p>O2-2 Sym'Previus-fungi: predicting spore germination and radial growth of fungi in dairy products</p> <p>Nicolas Nguyen Van Long, Marion Valle, Yvan Le Marc, <u>Jeanne-Marie Membré</u>, Catherine Denis, Janushan Christy, Valérie Michel, Valérie Stahl, Didier Majou, Emilie Gauvry, Emmanuel Jamet, Fanny Tenenhaus-Aziza, Jean-Christophe Augustin, Narjes Mtimet, Laurent Guillier, Sabine Jeuge, Anna Jofré, Alizée Guérin, Aline Rault, Stella Planchon, Louis Coroller 🇫🇷 🇪🇸</p>
14:00	<p>O2-3 Using shiny R package to develop a user-friendly interfaces powered by complex predictive microbiology models</p> <p>Dipon Sarkar, Mark Tamplin, Rajat Nag, Alberto Garre 🇫🇷 🇮🇹 🇪🇸</p>

14:15	<p>O2-4 Food Safety Knowledge Exchange (FSKX) format: current status and strategic development plans</p> <p><u>Matthias Filter</u>, Thomas Schüler </p>
14:30	<p>O2-5 Discovering Pathogens-in-Foods: resources and applications of a database on occurrence data of foodborne pathogens in European-marketed foods</p> <p>Ana Sofia Faria^{1,2}, Maiara Winter^{1,2}, Anne Thebault³, Laurent Guillier³, Pauline Kooh³, Winy Messens⁴, <u>Vasco Cadavez</u>^{1,2}, Ursula Gonzales-Barron </p>
14:45	<p>O2-6 e-Platon: an interactive web-based platform for spatio-temporal illustration of multi-metric laboratory food safety and quality data with capacity for real time, on-line multivariate analysis</p> <p><u>Panagiotis Skandamis</u>, Antonia Gounadaki </p>
15:00-15:30	<p>Coffee break Poster session The presenters with “odd number” should stand by the poster (1F Hall)</p>
15:30-16:00	<p>Software fair -1 Short presentation (5 min) of each software tool Chair: Shige Koseki</p>
15:30	<p>Food Safety Knowledge-Lab (FSK-Lab) Thomas Schueler,</p>
15:35	<p>D database, bioinactivation, biogrowth & biorisk - a complete toolset for predictive micro and QMRA Alberto Garre</p>
15:40	<p>FSSP Maryam Maktabdar</p>
15:45	<p>Sym’Previus Yvan Le Marc</p>
15:50	<p>MicroHibro Fernando Pérez Rodríguez</p>
16:00-18:00	<p>Software fair Software demonstration and hands on session at #1 meeting room (1st floor)</p>

Day 3:
Thursday, June 15, 2023

at 2F Auditorium

8:00-	Registration
8:30-9:00	<p>Keynote lecture 2 New developments in microbial heat inactivation: Setting the basis for a risk-based design in thermal processing of foods</p> <p>Prof. Kostas Kouthomanis (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece) 🇬🇷</p>
9:00-10:30	<p>Oral session 3: Advanced modeling technique Chairs: Maarten Nauta & Vasilis Valdramidis</p>
9:00 -	<p>O3-1 When the Weibull model helps in deciphering bacterial variability related to survival behaviour</p> <p><u>Jeanne-Marie Membré</u>, Ivan Leguérinel 🇫🇷</p>
9:15	<p>O3-2 Development of a thermal inactivation model considering the thermotolerance variability of 19 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> strains using the multi-variate normal distribution and the Most Probable Curve method</p> <p><u>Hiroki Abe</u>, Susumu Kawasaki 🇯🇵</p>
9:30	<p>O3-3 Understanding the relation between single-cell division times and growth dynamics of bacterial colonies</p> <p><u>Styliani Dimitra Papagianeli</u>, Zafeiro Aspidou, Konstantinos Koutsoumanis 🇬🇷</p>
9:45	<p>O3-4 Conditions Needed to Re-induce Lag Phase of Salmonella Under Dynamic Temperature Conditions</p> <p><u>Megan Wang</u>, Donald Schaffner 🇺🇸</p>
10:00	<p>O3-5 Dynamic Modeling of Interspecies Bacterial Competition – An Integrated Approach</p> <p>Lihan Huang 🇺🇸</p>

10:15 - 11:00	Coffee break Poster session The presenters with “ Even number ” should stand by the poster (1F Hall)
11:00- 12:15	Oral session 4: Optimization of food processing Chairs: Don Schaffner & Jukka Ranta
11:00	O4-1 The Use of Mathematical Modelling in the Optimization of Food Packaging Design for Vegetables to Avoid the Pack and Pray Approach: A Baby Leaf Spinach Case <u>Francesco S. Giordano</u> , Andrew Reynolds, Lorraine Foley, Jesus M. Frias 🇮🇹
11:15	O4-2 Optimising the selection of temperature levels in the experimental design for the estimation of cardinal parameters for growth <u>Ursula Gonzales-Barron</u> , Mariem Ellouze, Vasco Cadavez 🇪🇸 🇨🇭
11:30	O4-3 Tomato quality and safety assessment through the application of physicochemical and predictive microbiology models Francisco Jiménez-Jiménez, <u>Arícia Possas</u> , Laura Rabasco-Vílchez, Fernando Pérez-Rodríguez 🇪🇸
11:45	O4-4 Predicting the growth limits of psychrotrophic <i>Bacillus cereus</i> as a function of storage temperature, pH, water activity and acetic acid: an approach based on phylogenetic groups <u>Yvan Le Marc</u> , Anne Lochardet, Emilie Pétilion, Julie Evrard, Florence Postollec, Véronique Huchet 🇫🇷
12:00- 13:30	Lunch (HOTEL MYSTAYS Sapporo Aspen)
13:30- 15:00	Special session: Next Generation Predictive Modeling in the Food Industry; from mathematical models to Information Technologies (IT) and Data Science Organized by Prof. George -John Nychas (Greece) 🇬🇷
13:30	S-1 New Developments in Food Safety and Quality Assessment George – John Nychas 🇬🇷

14:00	S-2 The Machine Learning Web Platforms for Food Microbiological Quality and authentication Fady Mohareb
14:30	S-3 Risk-based Decision support in the Food Industry Konstantinos Koutsoumanis
15:00-15:45	Coffee break Poster session The presenters with “ Even number ” should stand by the poster (1F Hall)
15:45-17:30	Oral session 5: Predictive models based on new approaches Chairs: Jeanne-Marie Membré & Yvan Le Marc
15:45	O5-1 Overview: Rapid assessment of microbiological quality in meat and fish using FTIR Lemonia-Christina Fengou, Anastasia Lytou, <u>George Nychas</u>
16:00	O5-2 Modeling interactions between <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> and dominant bacteria in pasteurized milk Jiaming Zheng, Xiaofeng Li, Qingli Dong, <u>Xiang Wang</u>
16:15	O5-3 Data mining for predicting bacterial population behavior integrating food components <u>Kazuki Saito</u> , Shinya Sunagawa, Ryohei Shimizuhata, Shinji Nakaoka, Shige Koseki, Kento Koyama
	Chairs: Matthias Filter & Laurent Guillier
16:30	O5-4 Use of modelling to shed light on the enrichment ecology of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> Jasper Bannenberg, <u>Marcel H. Zwietering</u> , Tjakko Abee, Heidy M.W. den Besten
16:45	O5-5 Predicting bacterial growth and thermal inactivation in raw and cooked chicken meat during storage <u>Ibrahim Benamar</u> , Maarten Nauta, Samia Bellifa, Asma Cherif-Anntar, Omar Messaoudi, Mohamed Salih Barka, Boumedine Moussa-Boudjemaa

17:00	<p>O5-6 Effect of nutrient concentrations on the accuracy of predictive model for growth of <i>Escherichia coli</i> in foods <u>Masaki Kato</u>, Kento Koyama, Shige Koseki 🇯🇵</p>
17:15	<p>O5-7 Effect of benzalkonium chloride adaptation on the tolerance of <i>Cronobacter sakazakii</i> exposed to subsequent lethal stresses Hongmei Niu, Li Xu, Xiaojie Qin, Shuo Yang, Xu Wang, Xiang Wang, <u>Qingli Dong</u> 🇨🇳</p>
19:00-21:00	<p>Gala dinner at Sapporo Beer Garden “Genghis Khan” BBQ is Hokkaido's representative dish</p>

Day 4:
Friday, June 16, 2023

at 2F Auditorium

8:30-9:00	<p>Keynote lecture 3 Omics technologies for predictive microbiology: challenges and future directions</p> <p>Dr. Laurent Guillier (French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES), France) </p>
9:00-10:30	<p>Oral session 6: Predictive models based on various sources Chairs: Albert Garre & Fernando Perez-Rodriguez</p>
9:00	<p>O6-1 Modeling the effects of C18 free fatty acids on germination and emergence of vegetative cells as a function of their concentrations and degree of unsaturation</p> <p>Trunet Clement, Kaouache Sara, <u>Leguérinel Ivan</u> </p>
9:15	<p>O6-2 Assessment of microbial resistance under different pH and temperatures based on eGFP-labelled <i>Escherichia coli</i> strains</p> <p><u>Styliani Roufou</u>, Clara Buttigieg, Sholeem Griffin, Vasilis Valdramidis </p>
9:30	<p>O6-3 Survival prediction of dried <i>Bacillus cereus</i> based on glass transition temperature</p> <p><u>Tatsuya Inomata</u>, Kento Koyama, Shigenobu Koseki </p>
9:45	<p>O6-4 <i>Bacillus cereus</i> in dairy products: Prevalence and development of extensive growth and growth boundary models for mesophilic and psychrotolerant sub-groups</p> <p><u>Maryam Maktabdar</u>, Ellen Wemmenhove, Elissavet Gkogka, Lisbeth Truelstrup Hansen, Paw Dalgaard </p>
10:00	<p>O6-5 The antagonistic effect of lactic acid bacteria isolated from dairy products against food-borne pathogens: A systematic review and meta-analysis</p> <p>Yara Loforte, Nathalia Fernandes, André Martinho de Almeida, <u>Vasco Cadavez</u>, Ursula Gonzales-Barron </p>

10:15	<p>O6-6 Descriptive statistics and meta-analysis approaches to assess the effect of microbial contamination on the cultivation of microalgal biomass and its derivatives</p> <p><u>Haileeyesus Gebrehiwot</u>, Vasilis Valdradimis </p>
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee break and Poster session (1F Hall)
11:00-12:30	<p>Oral session 7: Applications of predictive models for various fields Chairs: Panagiotis Skandamis & Kento Koyama</p>
11:00	<p>O7-1 Listeria innocua inactivation in salami by process and by high pressure processing, how pragmatism can support the food safety</p> <p>Elena Cosciani-Cunico, Elena Dalzini, Paola Monastero, Stefania Ducoli, Marina-Nadia Losio </p>
11:15	<p>O7-2 A literature-validated sampling simulation characterizes the power of different sampling plans by simulating recalled and reference powdered infant formula batches</p> <p><u>Minho Kim</u>, Matthew Stasiewicz </p>
11:30	<p>O7-3 Effect of herbal extracts on the survival of S. aureus in goat's raw milk cheese</p> <p>Beatriz Nunes Silva, Sara Coelho-Fernandes, José António Teixeira, Vasco Cadavez, <u>Ursula Gonzales-Barron</u> </p>
11:45	<p>O7-4 Effect of non-thermal processings on allergenicity of shrimp tropomyosin</p> <p><u>Shuai Wei</u>, Xin Wang, Weicheng Hu, Shucheng Liu </p>
12:00	<p>O7-5 Multi-criteria decision technique to evaluate food safety and environmental impacts: Application to a large dairy farm</p> <p><u>Rodney Feliciano</u>, Jeanne-Marie Membré, Paola Guzman-Luna, Almudena Hospido </p>
12:15	<p>O7-6 Energy consumption model for liquid dairy products' heat treatment and cleaning-in-place processes in a plate heat exchanger system</p> <p><u>Maria Ioanna Malliaroudaki</u>, Nicholas J. Watson, Luanga N. Nchari, Satyajeet Bhonsale, Jan Van Impe, Rachel L. Gomes </p>

O7-3

Effect of herbal extracts on the survival of *S. aureus* in goat's raw milk cheese

Beatriz Nunes Silva^{1,2,3,4}, Sara Coelho-Fernandes^{1,2}, José António Teixeira^{3,4}, Vasco Cadavez^{1,2}, Ursula Gonzales-Barron^{1,2}

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Introduction: Raw milk cheeses have shown moderate prevalence of *S. aureus* (SA), imposing a health safety issue for consumers. Considering that lemon balm, sage and spearmint hydroethanolic extracts possess antimicrobial capacities, it was hypothesised that these could be used as biopreservatives in goat's raw milk cheeses during maturation.

Methodology: Lyophilised herbal extracts were produced using ethanol 70% (v/v) in a shaking water bath. Milk was inoculated with SA to reach ~5 log CFU/g and 1% (w/w) of each extract was added to the curd, while a non-inoculated control was kept. Cheeses were kept in a chamber at 10 °C/98% RH for 15 days. SA counts and pH were determined at specific days. For every treatment, a log-decay function with tail in differential form as primary model (with varying D-value), coupled to a secondary model Bigelow equation of D-value as a function of pH (with parameters $\log D_{ref}$ at pH 7.0 and z_{pH}) was adjusted.

Results: The dynamic models adequately fitted the survival curves, with RMSE of 0.1172, 0.0633 and 0.0567 for spearmint, lemon balm, and sage, respectively, producing significant parameter estimates. $\log D_{ref}$ was affected by the addition of extracts (0.621±0.061 for spearmint; 1.189±0.200 for lemon balm; 0.996±0.278 for sage), compared to the controls (0.932±0.166, 0.996±0.056 and 0.796±0.068). z_{pH} tended to be higher with the addition of spearmint (3.172±0.660) and lemon balm extracts (2.339±0.835), likely due to their interaction with the ongoing fermentation, but sage did not affect z_{pH} (2.006±0.677). The addition of plant extracts significantly decreased the time to achieve one log reduction, which in practical terms corresponded to up to 1.36 log CFU/g reduction by the end of maturation.

Conclusions and relevance: This work characterised SA survival parameters in goat's raw milk cheeses and demonstrated the usefulness of herbal extracts as biopreservatives against SA during cheese maturation. In this study, the antimicrobial properties of herbal extracts in foods were explored as a strategy to avoid the use of synthetic additives whose safety and impact on human health have been questioned in recent years.